

QUANTIFYING THE INFLUENCE OF LEARNING ACTION CELL TO THE PERFORMANCE OF TEACHERS

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Quantifying the Influence of Learning Action Cell to the Performance of Teachers

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Abstract

The Learning Action Cell (LAC) is defined as a collective of educators who participate in collaborative learning sessions to address common obstacles experienced within the educational institution. This study aimed at finding out if the extent of implementation of the school learning action cell sessions in terms of facilitation, resource speakers and materials is related to the teachers' school performance. The respondents of this study were the secondary public school teachers in Laak South District. A descriptive - correlational study was employed utilizing a universal sampling technique. Findings revealed that the extent of implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Facilitation and Resource Speaker is very high, while in terms of Materials it has a descriptive equivalent of high. Findings also revealed that the level of the performance of teachers in terms of self-management, teamwork, professionalism and ethics, result-focus, service orientation, innovation and individual performance commitment and review form (IPCRF) rating is high. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance to test the correlation of variables. Results show that there is no significant correlation between school learning action cell and teachers' performance. In conclusion, the extent of implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Facilitation and Resource Speaker is very high, while in terms of Materials it has a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that all indicators of the independent variable are perceived and observed very well by the respondents but it does not significantly correlates to the dependent variables which is the teacher's performance in school.

Keywords: *learning action cell (LAC), facilitation, resource speakers, teachers' performance, IPCRF rating*

Introduction

Teacher performance includes their ability to accomplish their tasks effectively which impact the growth and progress of pupils with extraordinary abilities. Indeed, empirical study demonstrates that teachers' performance is significantly influenced by their level of expertise, information, and inspiration. Educators are expected to deliver high-quality instruction and learning; therefore, they must meet these requirements and needs for high-quality education by obtaining extensive training and experience in teaching. In that regard, School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) serve as mechanism to enhance the teaching-learning process and facilitate teacher empowerment by encouraging cooperation, turning obstacles into strengths, and developing competencies (Jayson et al., 2021). In the Department of Education the Learning Action Cell sessions incorporate the elements of in-service trainings which aim to improve and enhance teachers' performance in schools. Through the program, instructors engage in tasks such as action planning, implementation, monitoring, evaluation, and reflection, leading to increased performance. But how can the teachers learn and participate wholeheartedly in the Learning Action Cell sessions if they are bombarded with paperwork, class preparations, instructional materials, and ancillary works?

The collaborative nature of School Learning Action Cell sessions and in service training creates a supportive environment that minimizes tasks, encourages collaboration, and improves instructors' well-being and instructional techniques. The study of Msamba et al. (2023) evaluates the impact of in-service education and training on teachers learning in Kilimanjaro and Manyara region of Tanzania. The finding indicated that in-service training effectively impacted teachers learning on subject knowledge, general knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge relating to competency-based teaching. Teachers' knowledge alone is vital, but it does not guarantee a change in classroom practice and students' outcomes. Therefore, it is equally essential that additional support such as follow-up, mentoring, coaching, peers, and school support of both resources and emotion continues to be provided for the impact to be extended from teachers' knowledge to classroom practices and improves learning outcome.

In the Philippines, many have studied the influence of the School Learning Action Cell (LAC) on the performance of teachers. Valdehueza et al. (2023) investigated the Learning Action Cell Instructional Designs and Teachers' Performance in Talakag II District, Division of Bukidnon, using a correlational design and a sample of 177 primary and secondary school teachers. The study's findings convey that the implementation of SLAC sessions is quite extensive, implying that these sessions are consistently observed and have a significant impact on the performance of teachers.

In the context of the local educational scenario, implementing School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) and Teachers' development programs is essential to facilitate teachers' performance and personal well-being. In fact, the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) conferences are scheduled once a month to inform teachers on the new trends in education, like re-echoing all the DepEd memorandum and upgrading teaching styles and strategies based on the learners' needs. However, even in this endeavor of giving learning sessions, it is still observable that many seasoned teachers need to develop even in their ample service in the department. For that reason, this initiative aims to assess the SLAC implementation level and its impact on teachers' performance of secondary public-school teachers.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the influence of School Learning Action Cell (LAC) on the Teachers' Performance of Secondary Public-School teachers in Laak South District. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of implementation of the School Learning Action Cell (LAC) in terms of:
 - 1.1. facilitation;
 - 1.2. resource speakers; and
 - 1.3. materials?
2. What is the level of academic performance of the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1. self-management;
 - 2.2. teamwork;
 - 2.3. professionalism and ethics;
 - 2.4. result-focus;
 - 2.5. service orientation;
 - 2.6. innovation; and
 - 2.7. Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) Rating?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the implementation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) and Teachers' Performance?

Literature Review

School Learning Action Cell

As stipulated in DepEd Order # 35 s. 2016, the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) is defined as a collective of educators who participate in collaborative learning sessions to address common obstacles experienced within the educational institution. The school principal or an assigned SLAC Leader oversees these sessions. School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) have the potential to evolve into educational institutions that foster healthy, compassionate, and secure communities of practice. Furthermore, the primary components of this process encompass continuous collaborative learning or problem-solving within a common professional domain, self-directed learning, and reflective practice resulting in action and self-evaluation, and collective competence.

The School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) serves as a collaborative platform within an organization, facilitating group discussions to share ideas and tactics that can be implemented or modified. The group learning session places significant emphasis on sharing trends, fostering creativity and innovation, and cultivating the adaptive skills necessary for individuals in the 21st century. Additionally, it emphasizes the diverse and efficacious approaches to delivering teaching (Culajara, 2023). The aims above are related to the promotion of both equity and excellence in the field of education. In order to accomplish this objective, instructional leaders and instructors must demonstrate persistence in augmenting their skills and knowledge by engaging in professional development opportunities. Professional development (PD) 's significance in improving educators' efficacy is well acknowledged. By employing this strategy, it is plausible to get enhanced efficiency and adaptability in response to the dynamic educational scene, facilitating ongoing progress in learning that corresponds with the substantial transformations induced by industrialization and globalization.

Facilitation of Learning Action Cell

According to the research conducted by Jayson et al. (2021) school learning action cell (SLAC) positively impacts teachers' performance by reducing tasks, promoting collaboration, enhancing instructional mastery, and increasing teacher efficacy in the workplace. In addition, Angela et al. (2023) indicated that the lived experiences of teachers in SLACs emphasized empowerment through collaboration, competency enhancement, and the importance of commitment and leadership in improving teaching quality. Facilitators have a pivotal role in facilitating the engagement of the learning set with underlying emotions and power dynamics, which can have positive and negative effects on the learning process. Bernhard (2023) asserts that the facilitators play a crucial role in exploring these dynamics within the set while fostering a secure environment for introspection and personal development.

Learning Action Cell Resource Speakers

In their study, Joseph and Raelin (2021) examine the role of the resource speaker in enhancing the learning action cell through their presentation on action learning as a valuable tool for human resource development and collaborative leadership. Indeed, utilizing action learning as a method for human resource development holds promise in enhancing the learning process of action cells for collective leadership improvement. The utilization of action learning as a means of work-based learning is prevalent, with its various components proving to help develop collective leadership abilities within organizational contexts (Benjamin et al., 2021).

Materials in the Learning Action Cell

Angela et al. (2023) assert that the learning action cell incorporates diverse technologies and materials within its framework and execution. According to Lucila and Pippa (2021), one of the obstacles encountered while utilizing materials in learning action cells is the necessity to comprehend the intricate relationship between the physical (material and digital), conceptual, and social dimensions of

learning, as well as their collective impact on emergent activity. Hence, Materials play a crucial role in the success of a school learning action cell (SLAC) by providing support and resources for teachers.

Teachers' Performance in School

Factors that contribute to teachers' performance in school include teacher level, teaching supervision, management program (training), conducive climate, facilities and infrastructure, physical and mental condition of teachers, motivation, leadership style of the principal, welfare assurance, managerial ability of the principal, emotional intelligence, organizational culture, work attitude, principal supervision, workgroup encouragement, relationships with the principal, dealing with unruly and aggressive students, work experience, work culture, enthusiasm and dedication, knowledge alignment, work motivation, discipline, and teacher interpersonal communication (Mualimah et al., 2019).

Self-Management and Teachers' Performance

Self-management and teachers' performance are important factors in education. Teachers' self-efficacy, classroom management, and time management techniques have been found to have a positive relationship with students' learning outcomes and class performance (Ciptro, 2021). According to Hafiz (2016), teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to solve problems faced by students and create a positive learning environment. Effective classroom management leads to increased student participation, enjoyment in the learning process, and higher motivation (Lon et al., 2023). Additionally, teachers' time management skills, particularly in lesson planning, have been found to positively impact class performance. Furthermore, self-evaluation of teachers' performance can contribute to improving the quality of their work and achieving institutional goals. However, it is important to note that some teachers may feel obligated to engage in self-evaluation rather than doing it willingly.

Professionalism and Ethics of Teachers

Educators can exhibit professionalism and ethical conduct in their professional endeavors through many approaches. To begin with, individuals can cultivate ethical competencies, such as ethical sensitivity, enabling them to make well-informed judgments about pupils from varied backgrounds within the context of inclusive education (Kirsi & Elina, 2022). Furthermore, educators must exhibit intentionality in their vocation, cultivating intrinsic drive and perseverance to sustain their arduous yet rewarding endeavors guided by overarching objectives (Sofia et al., 2022).

Result-Focus and Teachers' Performance

Result-focused teaching can lead to improved and enhanced teacher performance. According to Jason (2012) evaluating teacher effectiveness and providing information about it can enhance market functioning and improve children's education. Teacher efficacy, which can influence teacher effectiveness, can be positively impacted by creating a receiver-oriented environment in teacher-education classes (Maria, 2010). However, it is important to note that teacher performance cannot be solely attributed to teachers, as the decline or improvement of education standards and quality depends on various factors including the roles played by parents, learners, tertiary institutions, non-governmental organizations, and the government. Therefore, improving teacher performance requires a collaborative effort from all stakeholders and the restructuring of teacher training and school governing bodies (Nengwekhulu, 2008)

Teamwork and Teachers' Performance

Teamwork has a positive effect on teacher performance (Ahmad et al., 2022). Transformational leaders who are able to stimulate teachers and others play a crucial role in facilitating teamwork (Mohammad et al., 2022). Additionally, Machiel (2019) conveyed that team-oriented HR practices such as recruitment, team development, team evaluation, and teamwork facilitation are positively related to team innovation and efficiency in vocational education and training institutions. University teachers' team effectiveness has a positive impact on team performance, and team learning acts as a mediator between team effectiveness and team performance (Lixia & Xia, 2019).

Service Orientation and Teachers' Performance

Service orientation plays a significant role in teachers' performance. Studies have shown that individuals with a strong orientation to do good for others and for society are better oriented towards helping specific public service users, such as students. In-service training is an important aspect of improving teacher professionalism and performance. It has been found that in-service training programs have a significant effect on teachers' performance, as they address training needs and use effective strategies (Rose, 2018). Action orientation, as a facet of self-regulation, can also impact the prerequisites for successful teacher training. Different clusters of pre-service teachers with varying abilities to overcome failure and implement plans have been identified, which can inform support needs and educational interventions (Sandra, 2020).

Innovation and Teachers' Performance

Innovation positively affects teachers' performance by improving their ability to engage students, use diverse teaching strategies and methods, and incorporate technology into their lessons. Teachers' innovative teaching methods contribute to students' learning attitude, motivation, and skill development (Remya, 2022). Sulasmi (2023) argued that innovation is critical to improving teacher performance

across educational contexts. Studies emphasize the role of innovative leadership in boosting educator performance. Teachers' innovation performance is influenced by factors such as innovation attitude, positive anticipated emotion, group norms, and social identity.

Individual Performance Commitment and Review Portfolio (IPCRF) Rating of Teachers

Factors that influence the individual performance commitment and review portfolio rating of teachers include academic supervision, managerial competence, organizational commitment, and teacher empowerment (Imron et al., 2023). These factors have a significant positive effect on teacher performance and commitment. (Estrelle & Opeña, 2022). Additionally, Chun-Mei (2012) states that the integration of information and communication technology (ICT) in teaching plays a crucial role in improving teacher performance and commitment. Teachers' computer skills and knowledge, as well as their level of ICT integration in the classroom, are important factors in enhancing teaching and learning outcomes (Khushnuma et al., 2019).

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a quantitative, descriptive-correlational approach. A method was utilized to examine the situation, as it exists in its current state. Descriptive-correlational research approach involves identification of attributes of a particular phenomenon based on an observational basis, or the exploration of the correlation between two or more phenomena (Creswell, 2012). Moreover, this method also determines the significant relationship between the implementation of School Learning Action Cell (LAC) to the Performance of Teachers in the Secondary Public-School teachers in Laak South District. This research work entails obtaining data in order to test hypotheses or answer questions about the present research problem.

Respondents

The respondents of this study are the Secondary Public School Teacher of Laak South District. In the district there are six National High School Located at Barangay Mabuhay, Mangloy, Poblacion Laak, Kapatagan, Kilagding, and San Antonio, Laak Davao De Oro. This study will use universal sampling technique.

Table 1. *The distribution of respondents from the Secondary Public-Schools in Laak South District*

<i>Secondary Public Schools in Laak South District</i>	<i>No. of Teachers (Respondents)</i>
Mabuhay NHS	16
Mangloy NHS	5
Laak NHS	85
Kapatagn NHS	38
Kilagding NHS	5
San Antonio NHS	15
Total	164

Instruments

The data needed for this research were gathered through the use of a researcher-made questionnaire. Several references were read thoroughly to come up with rich details of literature which enlightened the researcher to come up with the survey questionnaire using the Five-point Likert Scale. The primary goal of this study is to know how well was the implementation of School Learning Action Cell is done among the 6 secondary public-school teachers in the Laak, South District, Division of Davao De Oro using the Core and Behavioral Competencies Indicators in the Result-Based Management System as a tool. This would be based on guidelines and each item is read by the participants.

Procedure

In gathering the data for this study, a letter was sent to the Department of Education Division of Davao de Oro for the approval of the conduct of the study to the identified schools in the district. The approved letter from the division was attached to the letter which was sent to the identified schools to request approval for the distribution of the questionnaire.

Before conducting the study, the researcher applied and accomplished the ethics review application form in order to really follow the ethical considerations before conducting the research.

During the distribution, the researcher explained the reason for the conduct of the study. The researcher was personally administering the questionnaire. Instructions as to the mechanics were given. The respondents were given enough time to answer, so the questionnaire was retrieved after 1 hour. When the respondents already finish answering, the researcher asked the Core Behavioral Competencies Rating and the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) Rating of the respondents which can be found in Phase 2 and 3 in their IPCRF 2022-2023.

The responses were tallied, tabulated, and subjected to statistical treatment. Findings were analyzed and interpreted to provide answers

to the research questions asked in the previous section.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results obtained from the collected data and the subsequent analyses and interpretation based on the problems presented.

Extent of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Facilitation

The implementation of Learning Action Cell (LAC) was evaluated in terms of Facilitation, Resource Speakers and Materials. Table 2 shows the implementation of Learning Action Cell (LAC) in terms of Facilitation.

Table 2. *Extent of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Facilitation*

<i>Items:</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
<i>With the facilitation of LAC, I was able to:</i>		
1. Assess the needs for self-management with reference to the professional development standards.	4.5	Very High
2. Develop teamwork in the workplace.	4.6	Very High
3. Show professionalism and ethics in dealing with the students, parents, and stakeholders.	4.6	Very High
4. Produce very satisfactory quality work.	4.4	High
5. Translates creative thinking into tangible changes and solutions that improves teaching.	4.4	High
6. Takes personal responsibility for dealing with students, parents, stakeholders and visitors for service issues and concerns.	4.5	Very High
Weighted Mean	4.5	Very High

Based on the result, among the indicators of facilitation, develop teamwork in the workplace and show professionalism and ethics in dealing with students, parents, and stakeholders got the highest rating of 4.6 with the description of very high. This means that this condition was observed at all times. The result implies that the SLAC sessions gave respondents the chance to practice and develop teamwork and camaraderie which will help perform better as a productive teacher. It also implies that SLAC facilitation ignites the teacher to show professionalism and ethics in dealing with the students, parents, and stakeholders. This shows that the SLAC sessions in terms of facilitation are substantial.

The other indicators with the same description and observed at all times are assess the needs for self-management with reference to the professional development standards with the mean of 4.5; takes personal responsibility for dealing with students, parents, stakeholders and visitors for service issues and concerns with 4.5. The results also generated the conditions that were observed most of the time with the respective means as Produce very satisfactory quality work, 4.4 and Translates creative thinking into tangible changes and solutions that improves teaching, 4.4. The overall mean of the Implementation of SLAC in terms of Facilitation is 4.5 which is perceived as very high among the teachers.

Extent of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Resource Speakers

Determining the influence of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) on the Teachers' Performance of Secondary Public-School teachers in Laak South District was one of the objectives of this research. Table 3 shows the Implementation of School Learning Action Cell in terms of Resource Speakers. The indicators of Implementation of SLAC sessions in terms of Speakers reflected an overall mean of 4.5 which indicates a very high descriptive equivalent. The result signifies that the implementation of School Learning Action Cell in terms of Resource Speakers is excellent.

Table 3. *Extent of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Resource Speakers*

<i>Items:</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
<i>During the LAC sessions, the Resource Speakers were able to:</i>		
7. Explain the objectives of the subject matter clearly at the beginning of every session.	4.6	Very High
8. Show smartness, confidence and firmness in making decisions.	4.5	Very High
9. Organize the presentation of the subject matters by systematically following LAC outline.	4.5	Very High
10. Use various strategies, teaching aids/devices and techniques in presenting the subject matter.	4.4	High
11. Update with present trends that are relevant to the subject matter.	4.4	High
12. Listen to the suggestions and opinions and is worthy of praise.	4.5	Very High
Weighted Mean	4.5	Very High

The result indicates that the SLAC resource speakers explain the objectives of the subject matter clearly at the beginning of every session as shown by the mean score of 4.6 reflected by very high description. This is followed by show smartness, confidence and firmness in making decisions with a mean score of 4.5; organize the presentation of the subject matters by systematically following LAC outline with a mean of 4.5; and listen to the suggestions and opinions and is worthy of praise with a mean of 4.5, described as very high. Meanwhile, use various strategies, teaching aids/devices and techniques in presenting the subject matter with a mean 4.4, and update with present trends that are relevant to the subject matter with a 4.4 mean. The overall mean of the Implementation of SLAC in terms of Resource Speakers is 4.5 which is perceived as very high among the teachers.

Extent of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Materials

Table 4 shows the extent of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in terms of Materials. The indicators of Implementation of SLAC sessions in terms of materials reflected an overall mean of 4.4 which indicates a high descriptive equivalent. The result signifies that the implementation of School Learning Acton Cell in terms of Materials is high.

Table 4. *Extent of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Materials*

Items:	Mean	Descriptive Rating
<i>In every LAC session, materials are:</i>		
13. Provided to attend all the LAC objectives in the subject matter.	4.3	High
14. Used successfully from the beginning until the end of the session.	4.4	High
15. Distributed adequately to every LAC member.	4.3	High
16. Appropriate for the subject matter and the level of the LAC members.	4.4	High
17. Utilized to ignite collaboration and innovations among the LAC members.	4.4	High
Weighted Mean	4.4	High
Overall Mean	4.4	High

The result indicates that the SLAC materials are used successfully from the beginning until the end of the session with a mean of 4.4; appropriate for the subject matter and the level of the LAC members with a mean of 4.4; and utilized to ignite collaboration and innovations among the LAC members with a mean of 4.4 with the descriptive equivalent of high which interpreted as the item embodied is observed most of the times. The result signifies that there is an enough materials which are utilized appropriately along the SLAC sessions. Meanwhile, provided to attend all the LAC objectives in the subject matter with a mean score of 4.3; and Distributed adequately to every LAC member with a mean 4.3, with the descriptive equivalent of high. The overall mean of the Implementation of SLAC in terms of Facilitation is 4.4 which is perceived as high among the teachers.

Level of the Performance of Teachers in Terms of Self-Management, Teamwork, Professionalism and Ethics, Result-Focus, Service Orientation, Innovation and Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) Rating

Table 5 shows level of the performance of teachers in terms of Self-Management, Teamwork, Professionalism and Ethics, Result-Focus, Service Orientation, Innovation and Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) Rating of the secondary school teachers in Laak South District, SY 2022-2023. As shown, it has an overall mean of 4.4 with a high descriptive equivalent.

Table 5. *Level of the Performance of Teachers in Terms of Self-Management, Teamwork, Professionalism and Ethics, Result-Focus, Service Orientation, Innovation and Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) Rating*

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. Self-management	4.3	Consistently Demonstrates(CD)
2. Teamwork	4.5	Role Model (RM)
3. Professionalism and Ethics	3.9	Most of the Time Demonstrates(MTD)
4. Result Focus	4.4	Consistently Demonstrates(CD)
5. Service Orientation	4.1	Consistently Demonstrates(CD)
6. Innovation	4.0	Consistently Demonstrates(CD)
7. IPCRF Rating	4.4	Very Satisfactory(VS)
Overall Teaching Performance	4.4	High

As shown in the table, among the indicators of Teachers' Performance teamwork got the highest rating of 4.5 with the description of role model. It implies that the secondary school-public school teachers in Laak South District develops and engaging milieu in which instructors operate is crucial in facilitating their willingness to take chances and engage in collaborative learning. This is followed by Result Focus with a mean score of 4.4; and the IPCRF rating with a mean score of 4.4, with the descriptive equivalent of very satisfactory. Meanwhile, self-management got the mean score of 4.3; service orientation with a mean of 4.1; innovation with a mean of 4.0; and professionalism and ethics with a mean score of 3.9. The overall mean of teaching performance is 4.4 which is perceived as high among the teachers.

Relationship between School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) and Teachers' Performance of Secondary Public School Teachers in Laak South District Shown in Table 6 are the results in the relationship between the implementation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) and Teachers' Performance.

Table 6. *Relationship between School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) and Teachers' Performance of Secondary Public School Teachers in Laak South District*

Variables	p-value	Correlation coefficient	Remarks
SLAC	0.275	0.086	Not Significant
Teachers' Performance			

Shown in Table 6 are the results in the relationship between the implementation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions and Teachers' Performance. Variables posted the following p-value and correlational coefficient results. The p-value is 0.275 which is

greater than .05, not significant and the correlation coefficient is 0.086. The result implies that the SLAC Facilitation, SLAC Resource Speakers and SLAC Materials are found to have no significant correlation with the teacher's performance. The p-value indicates the likelihood of a particular result being obtained purely by chance. In this case, the p-value is higher than 0.05, which suggests that there is not enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between the two variables being tested. Therefore, the result suggested that there is no significant relationship between implementation of school learning action cell and teachers' performance.

Extent of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Facilitation. The overall mean of the Implementation of SLAC in terms of Facilitation is very high among the teachers. The result implies that the impact of SLAC facilitation to the secondary public-school teachers in Laak South District as manifested behaviors that can interfere with better learning and it helps the teachers perform and develop professionally in the workplace. This is in connection with the idea of Jayson et al. (2021) that school learning action cell (SLAC) positively impacts teachers' performance by reducing tasks, promoting collaboration, enhancing instructional mastery, and increasing teacher efficacy in the workplace.

Angela et al. (2023) indicated that the lived experiences of teachers in SLACs emphasized empowerment through collaboration, competency enhancement, and the importance of commitment and leadership in improving teaching quality. Furthermore, the implementation of SLACs play a crucial role in fostering teacher growth, improving school performance, and creating a supportive professional environment.

Extent of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in terms of Resource Speakers. The overall mean of the implementation of SLAC in terms of Resource Speaker very high among the teachers. This result implies that the resource speakers planned and implemented the proper guidelines in conducting SLAC session which are in accordance with the Department of Education's call for schools to continuously provide professional community of practice that would empower teachers' productivity and performance. This is in congruence to the idea of Joseph and Raelin (2021) which examine the role of the resource speaker in enhancing the learning action cell through their presentation on action learning as a valuable tool for human resource development and collaborative leadership. Indeed, utilizing action learning as a method for human resource development holds promise in enhancing the learning process of action cells for collective leadership improvement.

According to Li (2019), integrating action learning into human resource development offers participants enhanced readiness for assuming collective leadership responsibilities. The utilization of this strategy has the potential to facilitate the attainment of collaborative leadership by offering a means for cultivating essential competencies and expertise (Mohammad et al., 2022). Furthermore, the study conducted by Monika et al. (2019) revealed the crucial elements that enhance the efficacy of resource speakers within the learning action cell. These elements encompass encouraged participation and self-organized cooperation, which serve as dialogical spaces that connect individuals' interests and facilitate constructive dispute resolution.

Extent of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in terms of Materials. The overall mean of the implementation of SLAC in terms of Materials is high among the teachers. This result implies that the materials during the SLAC sessions are used accordingly which promoted collaborations and improved the output teachers which helped in attaining the goal of SLAC sessions. Angela et al. (2023) assert that the learning action cell incorporates diverse technologies and materials within its framework and execution.

According to Lucila and Pippa (2021), one of the obstacles encountered while utilizing materials in learning action cells is the necessity to comprehend the intricate relationship between the physical (material and digital), conceptual, and social dimensions of learning, as well as their collective impact on emergent activity. Hence, Materials play a crucial role in the success of a school learning action cell (SLAC) by providing support and resources for teachers.

Level of the Performance of Teachers in Terms of Self-Management, Teamwork, Professionalism and Ethics, Result-Focus, Service Orientation, Innovation and Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) Rating. It shows the status of teachers' performance in the secondary-public school teachers in Laak South District, SY 2022 – 2023. As shown, it has a superior or very satisfactory description. The result implies that the teachers have develop teamwork, focused on the result, performed well in their work as speculated in the IPCRF rating. This is supported by Mualimah et al. (2019) mentioned many factors that contribute to teachers' performance in school include teacher level, teaching supervision, management program (training), conducive climate, facilities and infrastructure, physical and mental condition of teachers, motivation, leadership style of the principal, welfare assurance, managerial ability of the principal, emotional intelligence, organizational culture, work attitude, principal supervision, workgroup encouragement, relationships with the principal, dealing with unruly and aggressive students, work experience, work culture, enthusiasm and dedication, knowledge alignment, work motivation, discipline, and teacher interpersonal communication.

In addition, teamwork has a positive effect on teacher performance (Ahmad et. al., 2022). Cultivating interpersonal connections among staff members through communication channels, establishing a collective ideology, and the potential for recognition and familiarity from colleagues and supervisors can facilitate the development of practical cooperation (Adani et al., 2022). According to Meghan et al. (2013), administrators actively seeking and incorporating teachers' feedback regarding professional development initiatives help foster a sense of worth and belonging among instructors within the teaching community.

Moreover, result-focus can lead to improve and enhance teacher performance. According to Jason (2012) evaluating teacher effectiveness and providing information about it can enhance market functioning and improve children's education. Teacher efficacy, which can influence teacher effectiveness, can be positively impacted by creating a receiver-oriented environment in teacher-education classes (Maria, 2010).

Furthermore, there are factors that influence the individual performance commitment and review portfolio rating of teachers include academic supervision, managerial competence, organizational commitment, and teacher empowerment (Imron et al., 2023). These factors have a significant positive effect on teacher performance and commitment. (Estrelle & Opeña, 2022).

Relationship between School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) and Teachers' Performance of Secondary Public School Teachers in Laak South District. The result shows that there is a no significant relationship between the implementation of School Learning Action Cell and Teacher's Performance.

Several factors can affect the non-significant association between teachers' performance and school learning action cells (SLAC). According to a study of Lugtu (2023) on the blended learning teaching skills of English teachers, one important contributing element may be the absence of major demographic variations among participants.

Additionally, the study on the implementation of SLAC sessions and teachers' competences made clear that there may not always be a direct correlation between the degree of SLAC implementation and teachers' professional development in terms of behavioral and functional competencies (Alain et al., 2022).

Furthermore, Caballes (2023) stated that although SLAC sessions improve the pedagogy and well-being of teachers, it's possible that they don't adequately address the difficulties associated with teaching outside of one's field, which could restrict their ability to improve teachers' overall performance. The non-significant correlation between SLAC and teachers' performance can be attributed to all of these factors combined.

Conclusions

Based on the results, the Implementation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions are perceived and observed very well by the respondents but it does not significantly influence the performance of teachers. Considering that School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) as a school-Based Continuing Professional Development strategy which aims to enhance teachers performance, the undertaking of DepEd as to the implementation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) session Secondary Public School Teachers in Laak South District was unsuccessful since the result showed that the implementation does not significantly influence the teachers performance based on the Core Behavioral Competencies Rating and the IPCRF rating result in the school year 2022-2023.

Henceforth, based on the result the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the extent of implementation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) and Teachers' Performance is accepted.

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